

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

CHANGES IN THE SPECIES COMPOSITION OF SANDFLIES OF AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The article shows that leishmaniasis has been registered in Azerbaijan since the beginning of the twentieth century, and as a result of implementation of certain measures anthroponotic cutaneous leishmaniasis has been practically eliminated, foci of visceral leishmaniasis have been cured, and the number of bruises has sharply decreased. Recently, changes in the population and causes of recovery of leishmaniasis carriers have been shown.

Keywords: Phlebotomus, visceral leishmaniasis, cutaneous leishmaniasis, guide, insecticides, repellents, focus of disease

The geographical distribution of the various forms of leishmaniasis is extremely difficult to determine accurately. WHO noted the continuing expansion of leishmaniasis and emphasised that the increasing global incidence of the disease is a cause for concern. Leishmaniasis is more dangerous for the health of young people, as they are very sensitive and delicate at a young age and become ill more quickly than other age groups, while at the same time this age group is more likely to

be misdiagnosed. age group, and treatment of patients diagnosed with “black azar”, a form of leishmaniasis, is fatal in most cases.[1] Leishmaniasis is an obligately vector-borne parasitic disease known to be spread through rodents. These vectors belong to several genera of the group of two-winged group of arthropod type insects.

Pic1

In general, there is currently no clear view on the definition of taxonomic categories over species. About the family to which sandflies belong there is also a double opinion. Thus, some authors refer them to the family Phlebotomidae and others to the family Psychodidae. At the same time, there is no general opinion on the number of mollusc genera. The family Psychodidae (Phlebotomidae) is divided into 5 genera. Phlebotomia, Sergentomyia, Lutzomyia, Brumptomyia, Varileia. Sandflies known to carry leishmaniasis belong to the genus

Phlebotomus in the Old World and to the genus Lutzomyia in the New World.[1]

About 800 species of sandflies are known, of which more than 90 are vectors of leishmaniasis.

Other arthropod types (fleas, ticks) have been suggested to be vectors of leishmaniasis, and various experiments have yielded negative results.

Only 2 genera are found in Azerbaijan, namely species belonging to the genera Phlebotomus and Sergentomyia. Mosquitoes of the genus Sergentomyia are not vectors of diseases. Two forms of leishmaniasis -

anthroponotic cutaneous leishmaniasis (ACL) and Mediterranean visceral leishmaniasis (VL) - have been registered in Azerbaijan since the beginning of the 20th

century. The epidemiological chain of ACL is as follows: patient --- carrier ---- healthy person. Mediterranean VL includes dogs as a source of epidemiological disease.

Pic2

This situation poses issues that are important for the health care system to address, i.e. goals such as treatment of disease foci and elimination of the disease.[12] In this regard, in the 1960s of the twentieth century, the leishmaniasis control programme studied a number of issues related to their epidemiology, prepared a set of control measures and, as a result, carried out targeted activities. Within this complex, anthroponotic cutaneous leishmaniasis was practically eliminated, active foci of visceral leishmaniasis were cured, and the morbidity rate sharply decreased.[13,14]

In the spread of leishmaniasis in our country, sandflies as their vectors were also studied to some extent as one of the important components included in the epidemiological chain of the disease, i.e. bioecological characteristics of each source were studied. Sandflies in the locality, i.e. species composition, seasonal and diurnal activity, population density, and daytime refuges

were determined. The species of rodents naturally infected with Leishmania and their sensitivity to chemicals were further established.[3] It was tested both in the laboratory and in residential areas.[5,7]

As a result, 15 species were found to exist in Azerbaijan: *Ph. papatasi*, *Ph. sergenti*, *Ph. caucasicus*, *Ph. alexandri*, *Ph. mongolensis*, *Ph. jacusieli*, *Ph. transcaucasicus*, *Ph. tobbi*, *Ph. major*, *Ph. wenyoni*, *Ph. kandelakii*, *Ph. brevis* and *S. dentata*, *Ph. pawlinskyi*, *S. palesitensis*. Since sandflies of the genus *Sergentomyia* have no epidemiological importance as vectors, the following information will be limited to the genus *Phlebotomus*. A study of mosquito activity during the day showed that they become active with darkness in the evening.

Pic3.Diurnal activity of sandflies

They emerge from their daytime shelters and seek an object to suck blood. The time of their highest numbers is between 9pm and 1am. A slight increase is observed by 4am.[4]

As for the seasonal activity of sandflies, they are active for 4 months. When the weather warms up, sandflies emerge from the pre-diapause stage in the last days

Pic4. Seasonal activity of sandflies

Later, 30 years later, an outbreak of cutaneous leishmaniasis was again observed in the Shirvan Plain.[11] After specialists investigated, it turned out that it was cutaneous leishmaniasis caused by VL and not ADL, which had been recorded earlier. Such cases happen all over the world. For example, it has been reported in the south of France. So there is a conductor causing the disease.

I would like to point out that in addition to targeted vector eradication measures in the control of leishmaniasis, the chemicals used to kill Anopheles mosquitoes, which are vectors of malaria, have also had an impact on mosquitoes and led to a decrease in their numbers. This is because the biotopes of adult sandflies and mosquitoes are the same.[9] In the following years, attention to this problem decreased, there was no control and, of course, relevant studies were not carried out. In recent years, cases have been registered again in different regions and are gradually spreading to new territories.

The reasons for this situation are as follows:

Once malaria has been eliminated, mosquito eradication measures have not been implemented.

- Leishmaniasis could not be eliminated because the main foci were not sanitised.

- The shortage of specialists has had an impact.

- There is a lack of public education on protection against these diseases.

Our observations of recent years have revealed some nuances. It is these changes that characterise the current situation.

The population of sandflies has thinned, i.e. its density has decreased. For example, the number of sandflies sticking to the oiled paper used to catch them has now decreased 5-10 times.[8,10,15]

One change also concerns the species composition. The number of species constituting the sandflies fauna decreased, i.e. only 7-8 species were found out of

of May to the first decade of June. As you can see in the picture, the peak time of their numbers is on the 25th of June and the 1st decade of July. This is the 1st peak. Most of the second generation abundance covers the period from the 2nd decade of August to the 2nd decade of September.[3]

15 previously collected species. In subsequent years, according to the identification criteria adopted by systematists, some subspecies of sandflies were elevated to the status of species. Thus, 1 subspecies of *Ph.chinensis* species - *Ph.halepensis* - was elevated to the status of species. At the same time, according to A. Artemiev, sandflies previously designated in Azerbaijan as *Ph. mongolensis* should be designated not as this species, but as *Ph. jacusieli*. *Ph. mongolensis* is distributed in the Central Asian republics, but not in the Caucasian republics. The species *Ph. jacusieli* is found in the Caucasus republics.

Thus, taking into account the above, according to previous studies and literature data, the sandflies fauna of Azerbaijan includes the following species. *Ph. papatasi*, *Ph. sergenti*, *Ph. caucasicus*, *Ph. alexandri*, *Ph. jacusieli*, *Ph. transcaucasicus*, *Ph. tobbi*, *Ph. wenyoni*, *Ph. major*, *Ph. kandelakii*, *Ph. brevis*, *Ph. halepensis*, *Sergentyomia* sp. At the same time, the number of species decreased compared to previous years, not all species were found. Of course, our recent observations did not cover the whole Azerbaijan, which requires labour force. In any case, the results of the work so far show this.

The composition of sandflies fauna in different regions of our country should be clarified. To this end, observations should be made to determine the beginning, end and 2 maximum time of sandflies' summer per season, as some species may disappear, new species may be discovered. More than 30 years have passed since the study of leishmaniasis foci, and during this time works related to environmental problems and climate have been carried out in agriculture, recently there has been a multifaceted development of agriculture in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan. hyperurbanisation, hypermigration, significant changes in the en-

vironmental situation, which have not left sandflies unaffected and the resulting situation has also affected the population of sandflies.[13]

Given the above, the question arises. What should be done in such a case?

- It is necessary to organise active identification of patients in hospitals and involve them in treatment.

- Conduct surveillance of conductors, implement measures to control them and keep them under control during the period of their activity.

- Local medical staff should be aware of this problem and keep it under control.

- The yard where the sick person is registered and the yards around it should be treated

- Educate the public and show them how to protect themselves from sandflies.

- The importance of keeping yard areas clean and hygiene practices should be explained.

- To the extent possible, sick dogs should be identified and brought in for treatment. This work should be carried out under a joint contract with veterinarians and facilities that carry out this work.

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